

Groundwater Quality OF Durbawa, Toronka And Maruda Villages, Sheet 10 Sokoto SW, Northwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

Groundwater quality investigation of Toronka, Durbawa and Maruda villages, part of Sokoto Sheet 10 Sokoto, northwestern Nigeria covering an area of 30km² was carried out to determine its level of contamination and suitability for domestic and agricultural uses. Six (6) water samples were collected from various hand dug wells and boreholes in the three (3) villages in the study area. Physical and chemical parameters, such as electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), pH, and temperature, were evaluated using standard protocols. Both the chemical and heavy metal analyses were conducted at the Multi-User Laboratory, Umaru Musa Yara'adua University, Katsina using the AAS. The result indicated the average concentration of Mg²⁺ from the water samples is within the NSDWQ (2015) and WHO (2017) maximum permissible limit for drinking water except for Durbawa II (28.8 Mg/l) and Maruda II 27.2 Mg/l. Na⁺, K⁺, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻ and P are below the recommended WHO limit. Further, Ni²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Fe²⁺ concentration of some parts of the study areas were below the limits recommended by NSDWQ (2015) and World Health Organization WHO (2017) for human consumption. The Cr³⁺ was only found to be below the human consumption levels in samples from Durbawa II, but slightly higher in other samples while Pb²⁺ concentrations in all parts of the study areas were within the standard except in samples from Toronka Dakare where it slightly exceeded the standard. The Schoeller and Piper diagrams showed the dominant water type in the study area to be Ca-Mg-HCO₃ and precipitation domain due to the dissolution of carbonate rocks. Thus, the water in the study areas is slightly contaminated and required proper treatment if it is going to be used for agricultural and domestic purposes.

Keywords: Contamination; Heavy metal; Physico-chemical; Suitability; Water type

1.0 Introduction

The chemistry of water can lead to adverse effects either if there is an absence of necessary constituents or, more commonly, if there is an excess of a harmful chemical in the water. Drinking water standards are based on two main criteria: (i) presence of objectionable taste, odour, or colour, and (ii) the presence of substances with adverse physiological effects [1]: [2]. Safe drinking water is a basic need for good health, and it is also a basic right of humans [3]. Improved water supply is one of the essentials for a healthy lifestyle, constrained by uncontrolled anthropogenic activities [4]; [5], flow of pollution

from upland to lowland, too much use of fertilizers, pesticides in agriculture [6].

The aim of this study was to determine the groundwater quality of Durbawa, Toronka and Maruda Villages with the objectives of determining the groundwater quality through the use of physicochemical properties and evaluate heavy metals contamination level and determine its potability for domestic and agricultural activities.

Numerous authors, including [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [11]; [12]: [13]: [14]: [15] and others studied the Cretaceous and Paleogene sediments of the

Sokoto Basin. The sediments are found to be dipping gently and progressively thickening towards the northwest, with a maximum thickness of over 1000 meters near the Niger Republic border. These authors proposed several geological successions. Previous research focused primarily on the basin's stratigraphy, sedimentology, paleontology, and geochemistry. Geologic research in the Sokoto district dates back to the late 1800s, but most of the scientific literature is limited to general geologic findings or descriptions of fossil localities. [7] conducted the first major stratigraphic study in the Sokoto region. [8] updated previous work and mapped the geology of a large portion of Sokoto Province. [16], noted that the basin's sedimentary rocks range in age from Cretaceous to Tertiary and are primarily composed of interbedded sand, clay, and some limestone. The Mesozoic rifting and separation of Africa and America resulted in the formation of the Sokoto Basin, [17]. The Maastrichtian sediments of the Sokoto Basin come from brackish water and marginal marine environment, with white, grey, and brown siltstones, friable sandstones, clay stones, and biogenic structures. Sedimentary structures such as abundant bioturbation, repetitive bedding, and wavy bedding affirm that it is a tidal flat depositional environment. Those of marginal marine origin include shales, limestones, and mudstones containing vertebrate fragments, [18]. In the Sokoto Basin, three deposition phases have been identified. These include the pre-Maastrichtian continental phase, the Maastrichtian-Paleocene marine phase (in part), and the upper Tertiary continental phase [19].

groundwater in the study area for domestic and agricultural uses.

2.0 Study Area

The study area is around Toronka, Durbawa, and Maruda villages near Sokoto, northwestern Nigeria. It is located between latitudes 12° 39' 00" and 12°36' 00" N and longitude 4°30'00" and 4°33'00"E and covers an area of 30 km². The study area is part of Paleocene Dange and Kalambaina formations and is accessible through Sokoto-Guga-Maruda-Durbawa road, with several foot paths and untarred roads. The relief of the study area consists of flat-topped hills with ironstone capping which is dominated by gullies which serves as drainage to some of the surrounding villages. The study area is drained by River Sokoto and its tributaries which provide extensive floodplains for farming activities as shown in (Fig 1). The area is characterized by a short period of rainfall that really exceeds 5 months with a yearly average precipitation of about 600 mm. The rainfall is erratic with longer dry season that lasted from October to April, characterized by high temperature, low humidity with high evapotranspiration which can exceed 2,500 mm/year [20]. Vegetation in the area is characterized by sparse shrub and short feathery grasses, which forms a complete ground cover during the wet season only. The study area is part of the Nigerian sector of the Iullemeden Basin in north-western Nigeria which is underlain by a sequence of semi-consolidated sedimentary rocks ranging in age from Cretaceous to Tertiary and consisting mostly of interbedded sand, clay, and limestone.

This work is to employ hydrochemistry to determine the suitability of the surface and

Figure1: Location map of the study area.

3.0 Materials and Methodology

Geological mapping of the study area was done using necessary and suitable field instruments such as the field notebook, Sample bag, for collecting rock samples, GPS, compass clinometer, TDS Meter, pH and Temperature meter, and Electrical conductivity (EC) meter, Base map which indicates settlement and topography. Sampling coordinates were taken using the GPS (Global Positioning System), which was recorded in the field notebook and on the map for easy location and traversing.

There are different sources of water supply in the areas such as borehole, stream and hand-dug wells which serve as sources of collecting water samples for geochemical analysis. At the visited locations borehole waters were stored in overhead tanks in the compounds and some are made accessible for public use outside the compounds. Six (6) samples were collected in all, two (2) boreholes and four(4) hand dug well in different communities within the study area Table 1. The [21] criteria were followed for sampling, handling and analysis. Prior to the sampling, the containers were rinsed with water from which the

samples were to be collected; in order to get representative samples, direct from the aquifer. Water was pumped out using a water drawer from the different groundwater sources for at least 10 –15 minutes. Two samples were collected from each of the sampling points, in one sample from which the cations were to be analyzed and few drops of 1.1 molar HNO₃ was added to reduce the precipitation of some metals by reducing the pH of the water to 2. Physical parameters of electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS) pH, and temperature were measured in-situ at the sampling points using a handheld 3-in-1 conductivity and pH meters, respectively. Samples were stored at a very low temperature of 4°C [22]. The samples were taken to the multi-user laboratory of Umaru Musa Yara'adua University, Katsina, where they were processed and analyzed for major and minor cations, anions, and oxides using an atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS model AA 6300 SHIMADZU Japan). The Piper and Schoeller plots were employed through the hydrochem computer software for the samples to know the water types and the level of contamination and relative concentration of the anions and cations in the study area.

Table 1: Sources of drinking water in Durbawa and Toronka Villages and their coordinates

Sample No.	Location	Coordinates	Water Source
1.	Durbawa	13° 3' 33"N5° 20' 14"E	Borehole
2.	Durbawa II	13° 3' 38"N5°20' 18"E	Borehole
3.	Toronka Dakare	13° 3' 22"N5° 19' 39"E	Well
4.	Toronka Gujiyya	13° 3' 21"N5° 19' 29"E	Well
5	Maruda I	N 13° 3' 21" 5° 19' 29" E	Well
6	Maruda II	N 13° 3' 1" 5° 18' 16" E	Well

3.1 Laboratory Analysis (Hydrogeochemical)

Six (6) samples were collected and taken to Multi User Laboratory Umaru Musa Yara'adua University, Katsina for further analysis of major and minor elements and oxides analysis using Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) [23] and [24]. The chemical study was carried out on four water samples, two from each of the locations with the intent of determining the quality of the water sources such as borehole and hand-dug well, used for drinking and domestic purposes. The four water samples were analyzed for major elements and important anions. The cations Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺ were determined using atomic absorption spectrometer and Na⁺ was

analyzed using a flame photometer. The anions Cl⁻, and NO₃⁻ were determined using titrimetry. Water samples collected from the locations undergo laboratory tests. The piper Diagram was used to evaluate and interpret and define the sources of the hydro-chemical variables in the analyzed water samples from the study area.

The results were compared with recommended standards to determine the water geochemistry and its quality for drinking and domestic purposes.

4.0 Result

The analysis carried out on the six (6) samples includes physical parameters Table 2, whereas the major oxides and minor elements are

displayed in Tables 3 and 4 respectively. The physical parameters were measured in-situ at the point of sampling, while the major and minor elements were carried out in the laboratory.

Table 2: The physical parameters of the water samples as measured on the field

S/N	Sampling Location	Coordinates	pH	EC (ms/cm ⁻¹)	TDS (mg/l)
1	Durbawa	13° 3' 33"N 05° 20' 14"E	7.11	270	136
2	Durbawa II	13° 3' 38" N 05°20' 18"E	5.90	232	115
3	Toronka Dakare	13° 3' 22"N 05° 19' 39"E	5.97	70	35
4	Toronka Gujjiya	13° 3' 21"N 05° 19' 29"E	7.30	110	55
5	Maruda I	13° 3' 21"N 05° 19' 29"E	7.29	434	227
6	Maruda II	N 13° 3' 1"N 05° 18' 16"E	7.43	650	325
	Minimum	-	5.90	70	35
	Maximum	-	7.43	650	325
	Average	-	6.83	294.33	148.83
	[25] Standard (2015)	-	6.5-8.5	1000	500
	[26] Standard (2017)	-	6.5-8.5	-	1000

Table 3: The major elements and oxides concentration values

Sample Location	Na ⁺ (Mg/l)	K ⁺ (Mg/l)	Ca ²⁺ (Mg/l)	Mg ²⁺ (Mg/l)	PO ₄ (Mg/l)	CO ₃ (Mg/l)	HCO ₃ (Mg/l)	SO ₄ (Mg/l)	Cl (Mg/l)	NH ₃ (Mg/l)	NO ₃ (Mg/l)	DO (Mg/l)	BOD (Mg/l)
Durbawa I	2.0	7.0	42.0	31.2	0.07	0.8	NIL	0.02	2.6	0.6	0.8	2.4	14.8
DurbawaII	9.0	2.0	26.0	28.8	0.08	BDL	12.0	0.06	3.5	0.8	0.2	3.0	15.8
Toronka Dakare	2.0	1.0	24.0	22.8	0.07	BDL	8.0	0.04	4.8	0.6	0.8	5.0	17.0
Toronka Gujjiya	7.0	1.0	26.0	15.6	0.07	BDL	8.0	0.04	5.2	0.4	0.6	4.1	16.7
Maruda I	9.0	1.0	28.0	32.4	0.07	0.4	BDL	0.07	6.0	0.6	0.4	3.4	18.0
Maruda II	12.0	2.0	42.0	27.6	0.08	1.0	BDL	0.09	4.0	0.6	1.4	4.0	11.8
Minimum	2.0	1.0	24.0	15.6	0.07	0.8	8.0	0.02	2.6	0.4	0.2	2.4	14.8
Maximum	12.0	7.0	42.0	31.2	0.08	0.08	12.0	0.06	5.2	0.8	0.8	5.0	16.7
Average	6.83	2.33	31.33	26.4	0.07	0.8	9.33	0.05	4.35	0.6	0.7	3.65	26.89
[26]	50	10-150	20-300	10-150	4	120	300	250	250	0.5	50	5	5
[25]	200		200	10-150			300	250	250	0.5	50	5	5

5.0 Discussion

The pH is an important parameter in evaluating the acid–base balance of water as it serves as the indicator of acidic or alkaline condition of water. The pH value for studied samples ranges from 5.90–7.30 and average value is 6.6 which are in the range of [25] and [26] standards (6.5 to 8.5). Electrical Conductivity (EC) is amount of dissolved solids in water determines the electrical conductivity if their ions enhance conducting electric current. According to [25], EC value

should not exceed 1000ms/cm⁻¹. Samples from study area have EC value which ranges from 70-270ms/cm⁻¹ with an average value of 170 mscm⁻¹. This clearly indicates the water in the study area was not considerably ionized and has the lower level of ionic concentration activity due to small dissolve solids. Water has the ability to dissolve a wide range of inorganic and some organic minerals or salts such as potassium, calcium, sodium, bicarbonates, chlorides, magnesium, and sulfates. These minerals produced unwanted taste and diluted color in appearance of water. The

water with high TDS value indicates that water is highly mineralized. TDS value for the water samples ranges from 35 and 136 mg/l with an average value of 85.25 mg/l which is within the limit of [25] and [26] standards. High values of TDS in groundwater are generally not harmful to human beings, but high concentration of these may affect persons who are suffering from kidney and heart diseases. Water containing high solid may cause laxative or constipation effects [27]. The results of the major elements and oxides measured for the samples as shown in Table 4 indicate sodium Na^+ concentration ranges from 2.0 to 9.0 mg/l (Fig. 2a) with an average value of 5 mg/l and K^+ concentration in study areas ranges from 2.0 to 7.0 mg/l, with an average value of 2.75 mg/l (Fig. 2b) which is within the [25] and [26] maximum permissible limit for drinking water.

Figure 2 a and b: Chart of Sodium and Potassium concentration of the study area against [26] standard.

In the study areas, results show that the concentration of Ca^{2+} ranges between 24.0 to 42.0 mg/l and the average concentration is 29.5 mg/l (Fig. 3a) which is permissible for drinking and domestic activity after [26].

A

B

Figure 3: Chart of Calcium (A) and Magnesium (B) concentration of samples from study area against [26] standard.

Magnesium Mg^{2+} is an essential for proper functioning of living organisms and found in minerals like dolomite, magnetite etc. Human body contains about 25 g of magnesium (60 % in bones and 40 % in muscles and tissues) [3]. According to [26] the maximum permissible range of Mg^{2+} in water should be 30 mg/l, while according to [25] its maximum permissible limit for drinking water is 20 mg/l. In the study area Mg^{2+} ranges from 15.6 to 31.2 mg/l in Durbawa, Toronka, and its environs and the mean value of Mg^{2+} in water is 24.6 mg/l. The results exhibit high concentration of Mg^{2+} Fig.3b in Durbawa and its environs is above [25] and [26] maximum permissible limit for drinking water. This can be as a result of the geology of the study area is highly rich in Mg^{2+} , in which the running water dissolved it and infiltrate it down into the groundwater. Running water from a very far area can also be in contact with lithology that has high concentration of Mg^{2+} such as Dolomite, dissolved it at high amount, infiltrate it down to the ground water from which the aquifers of the study area are recharging or the aquifers are recharging Kalambaina limestone which have associated dolomite.

Bicarbonate HCO_3^- is a natural component of all mineral waters. Mineral waters that are sourced from limestone-rich areas typically have high

bicarbonate content. Bicarbonate plays a vital role in buffering acids and ensures that the mineral water tastes pleasantly clean and refreshing. The [26] allows maximum permissible limit of HCO_3^- 400 mg/l in drinking water. The concentration of HCO_3^- in the study area range between 8.0-12.0 Mg/l and the average concentration is 9.33 Mg/l Fig. 4a. These results indicate that the quantity of bicarbonate in the study site is acceptable. The chart below displays the concentration of bicarbonates from the water the study area

A

B

Figure 4a and b. Chart of Bicarbonates and Sulphates concentration of the study area against [26] standard.

Sulphate SO_4^{2-} mainly is derived from the dissolution of salts of sulphuric acid and abundantly found in almost all water bodies. High concentration of SO_4^{2-} may be due to oxidation of pyrite and mine drainage etc. Sulphate SO_4^{2-} concentration in natural water ranges from a few to a several 100 mg/l, but no major negative impact of SO_4^{2-} on human health is reported, [3]. The [25] has established 100mg/l as the highest desirable limit of SO_4^{2-} in drinking water and [26] established its maximum permissible limit in drinking water as 250mg/l. In study area, concentration of SO_4^{2-} ranges from 0.02-0.06 mg/l in Toronka, Durbawa and Maruda and the average value of SO_4^{2-} is 0.04 mg/l Fig. 4b. The result shows the concentration of sulfate in the study area is lower than the [25] and [26]

maximum permissible limit for drinking water. According to [25] and [26], concentration of Cl^- for drinking water should not exceed 250 mg/l. In the study area, the Cl^- value ranges from 5.2-2.6 Mg/l Fig. 5a in Toronka, Durbawa and Maruda villages, with an average value of 4.03 Mg/l.

A

B

Figure 5a and b: Chart of Chloride concentration of the study area against [26] standard.

Ammonia NH_4 in the environment originates from metabolic, agricultural and industrial processes and from disinfection with chloramines. Natural levels in groundwater and surface water are usually below 0.2 Mg/l. anaerobic groundwater may contain up to 3 Mg/l in the study area the calculated concentration of NH_4 from the titration analysis ranged from 0.4 to 0.8 Mg/l After [26] standard, water that has NH_4 concentration above 3.0 Mg/l is unsuitable for drinking. Hence the NH_4 in the water sample from the study area is above the [25] and [26] standard limit. Therefore, the water can be harmful for drinking and other domestic uses.

Nitrate NO_3^- is one of the most important diseases causing parameters of water quality particularly blue baby syndrome in infants. The sources of nitrate are nitrogen cycle, industrial waste, nitrogenous fertilizers and so on, [25]. [25]

and [26] allows maximum permissible limit of NO_3^- 50 mg/l in drinking water. In study areas, results more clear that the concentration of NO_3^- ranges from 0.2 to 0.8 Mg/l Fig. 6 in the study area with an average value of 0.6 mg/l. These results indicate that the quantity of NO_3^- in the study site is acceptable. The chart below show the concentration of nitrate compared with the [25] standard value for nitrate in drinking water.

Figure 6: Chart of Nitrate concentration of the study area against [26] standard.

Cadmium Cd^{2+} is a non-essential heavy metal that can be release to water from the corrosion of some galvanized plumbing. The primary origin of cadmium is by volcanic eruption in which is occur in extrusive igneous rocks such as Basalt which is found associated with zinc, lead and copper ores. The running water can be in contact with these Basalts or ores, dissolved the cadmium metal, infiltrate and concentrate it in ground water either in high concentration or low depends on the time taken for the water to remain in contact with the basalt, ore and their solubility. Since its non-biodegradable when ingested at high concentration it causes cardiovascular diseases including hypertension, atherosclerosis, nephropathy and diabetes. The concentration of cadmium in the study area ranges between 0.0018 to 0.0108 mg/l and the average concentration is 0.0078 mg/l. The [25] and [26] allows maximum permissible limit of cadmium 0.003 mg/l in drinking water. As seen in Figure 8 the concentrations of cadmium in samples from the study area is above the [25] and [26] maximum permissible limit for drinking water. Cadmium is a compatible element which occur either naturally in Basement complex found associated with zinc and lead or by anthropogenic sources such as smelting and incineration of municipal waste such as plastics and nickel-cadmium batteries which can be deposited as solid waste. The concentration of cadmium in the study area

ranges from 0.0002-0.0007 mg/l Fig. 7a which is below the [25] permissible limit of 0.003 mg/l.

A

B

Figure 7a and b: Cadmium and chromium concentration of the study area against [26] standard

Chromium (Cr^{3+}) is a non-essential, heavy metals found naturally in rocks and soils or release by anthropogenic activities. It occurs in combination with other elements as chromium salts some of which are also soluble in water. When ingested at high concentration it causes diseases including risk of lung, nasal and sinus cancer. Cr^{3+} is analyzed in all the samples locations, and ranges from 0.0041-0.0332 Fig. 7b which makes the water in the study area safe for domestic use as it is below the [26] standard permissible limit.

Iron Fe^{2+} concentration in the study area for all the samples ranges between 0.0035-0.0156 Mg/l Fig. 8a respectively. Therefore, all the samples have values far below the [26] permissible limit for drinking and other domestic activities which is 0.3 Mg/l.

A

B

Figure 8a and b: Iron and Nickel concentration of the study area against [26] standard.

The concentration of Nickel Ni^{2+} measured from the water samples varied between 0.0030-0.0051 Mg/l Fig. 8b, which is lower than the WHO (2017) permissible limit for drinking water which is 0.02 Mg/l. The concentration of lead Pb^{2+} from the sample water varied between 0.0041mg/l and 0.0074 Fig. 9, with average concentration 0.0081 mg/l. The lead Pb^{2+} is only slightly high in the water sample from Toronka Dakare which was above permissible limit of [25] and [26] for drinking water, 0.01mg/l. Exposure to lead is associated with wide range of effects. Young

children, infants, fetuses are particularly vulnerable to lead because the physical and behavioral effects of lead occur at lower exposure level in children than in adults. A dose of lead that would have little effect on adults can have a significant effect on a child. In children, low level exposure have been linked to damage to the central and peripheral nervous system, learning disabilities, shorter stature, and for adult exposure to lead can causes cardiovascular effect, increase blood pressure and decrease in kidney function [26]

Figure 9: Chart of Lead concentration of the study area against [26] standard.

Piper and Schoeller diagrams Fig. 10 and 11 computed using hydrochem computer software reveals that all the six (6) groundwater samples are rich in calcium, magnesium and bicarbonates. Therefore, the hydrofacies of the water in the study area are characterized by Ca-Mg- HCO_3 type as shown in the Fig. 10. The level of contamination and relative concentration of the anions and cations in the study area indicate shallow fresh groundwater that is slightly hard. The water is associated with limestone underlining the area and carbonate hardness from recent precipitation occurring at shallow depths below the surface [15].

Figure 10: Piper Diagram for samples in the study area.

Figure 11: Schoeller diagram showing level of contamination in the analyzed water sample in the study area.

6.0 Conclusion

Groundwater quality of drinking water sources in Durbawa and its environs was conducted to determine the contamination status. Results revealed groundwater with the physical parameters such as electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solid (TDS), and potential of hydrogen (pH) value of the study area were all analyzed in-situ fall within the Nigerian Standard Water Drinking Quality [25] and [26] standards. The concentration of Sodium Na^+ , Potassium K^+ , chloride Cl^- , Sulphate SO_4^{2-} , Nitrate NO_3^- , Bicarbonate HCO_3^- and Ammonia NH_4^+ of the collected water samples all fall under the maximum permissible limit by [25] and [26] and there were no toxicity problem. Magnesium (Mg^{2+}) concentration in Durbawa I, Durbawa II and Maruda I are above [26] maximum permissible limit recommended for drinking water. But all the remaining sample have Magnesium (Mg^{2+}) concentration below the minimum permissible limit recommended by [25] and [26] for drinking water. Heavy metals like Nickel Ni^{2+} , Cadmium Cd^{2+} Chromium Cr^{3+} are all within permissible limit. But Lead Pb^{2+} is only slightly high in the water sample from Toronka Dakare which was above permissible limit of [25] and [26] for drinking water, 0.01mg/l.

The people of Durbawa and its environ largely depend on these water source for drinking and domestic use without any treatment. However, if the water is to be consumed especially at Toronka Dakare village, proper treatment is necessary to avoid adding to the already existing health issues that affect not only older people but also children and younger people.

7.0 References

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